

Computational history of chemistry: The evolution of the chemical space and its interplay with the periodic system

Jürgen Jost¹ and Guillermo Restrepo²

¹jjost@mis.mpg.de, ²restrepo@mis.mpg.de

Max Planck Institute for Mathematics in the Sciences, Inselstraße 22, Leipzig, 04103 (Germany)

Abstract

Matter transformations have been curated and annotated by chemists for centuries. Today those records are part of large electronic databases. Here we show how such a corpus of information gathering millions of chemical reactions and substances is used to shed light on the large-scale processes of the evolution of chemistry, in particular on the discovery of chemicals and reactions constituting the chemical space. We show that chemical space has grown at an exponential rate, doubling every 16 years. By studying the variability of the annual output of chemicals between 1800 to the present, we observed that chemical production has undergone three statistical regimes. We found that World Wars have not affected the growth rate of the space, opening up new questions about the recovery of chemistry after these setbacks. We also explored the influence of chemical space upon the evolution of the periodic system. By studying the order and similarity between chemical elements over time, we found that despite six regimes of relative stability, the periodic system has converged over time to its current structure. In this work, we explore the history of chemistry using Big Data and computational approaches, a field of research we call computational history of chemistry.

Introduction

The increasing amount of data and of computational power are turning computational approaches an integral part of the historians' tools (Gibson et al., 2019). In addition to providing new ways to solve historical questions, computational history allows for asking and solving novel questions related to large scale patterns (Laubichler et al., 2013). Chemistry, being the science with the largest output of publications associated with its exponential growth of new substances, is therefore not short of data, which began to be systematically recorded in the 19th century (Jost & Restrepo, 2022). This data on the material system of chemistry is today available in electronic form and constitutes an opportunity to carry out computational studies on the history of chemistry (Restrepo, 2022a). Here we review recent results on the analysis of the annual output of new chemicals from 1800 up to 2015 (Llanos et al., 2019). We also discuss results on the relationship between such a material output and the evolution of one of the core concepts of chemistry, namely the periodic system (Bran et al., 2022; Leal et al., 2022).

The evolution of the chemical space

By *chemical space* we mean the substances reported over the history of chemistry, which are endowed with a notion of nearness (Jost & Restrepo, 2023; Restrepo, 2022b). Chemists have figured out chemical spaces of two sorts, one where substance nearness is provided by resemblance and another one encoding reachability (Restrepo, 2022b). The former treats resemblance in terms of substance properties, for instance physical properties, where the closer the values of those properties the more similar the substances are. This also involves resemblance at the molecular level description, where two substances are similar if their associated molecular structures hold a high degree of resemblance. A large part of mathematical chemistry has been devoted to mapping molecular structures to real values, which in turn are used to locate substances in the spaces generated by those values (Restrepo, 2022b). Chemical spaces based on the notion of reachability encode reaction networks. In this setting, any two substances are near if the number of reactions required to connect them is low. The recent widespread adoption of networks as a suitable model for different complex and dynamical

systems have led to the formulation of different network models for chemical reactions, which include directed graphs, Petri nets and directed hypergraphs (Restrepo, 2022b).

Our approach to the chemical space is based on the reachability setting, which therefore is based on the number of known substances and reactions at a given time in history. Such an approach therefore requires historical data on the discovery of substances and reactions. This information is today at our fingertips thanks to the encyclopaedic efforts of chemistry across history (Jost & Restrepo, 2022). Information on reactions and substances, besides being curated and annotated by leading figures such as Leopold Gmelin (1788-1853) and Friedrich Konrad Beilstein (1838-1906) is today available in digital form thanks to chemoinformatic initiatives of the 1990s. This has led to large databases of chemical information such as Reaxys, owned by Elsevier, and SciFinder, hosted by the American Chemical Society. These sources offer important information about the chemical space and its evolution. Reaxys, in particular, spans the largest temporal period, with reliable data from 1800 up to date.

Equipped with such a large corpus of chemical information gathered in Reaxys, we addressed the following questions: how does the chemical space grow? How rapidly? How are its dynamics affected by social perturbations such as wars? Is it perturbed by semiotic changes such as the introduction of new theories?

Growth of the chemical space

In 1963 de Solla Price briefly discussed the annual report of some chemical starting materials and the growth of chemical elements (Price, 1963). The first complete account of the growth of the chemical space was reported by Joachim Schummer in 1997, who analysed the period 1800-1995 by manually screening the indexes of eight printed sources, including handbooks of organic and inorganic chemistry (Schummer, 1997). He found an exponential growth with an annual growth rate $r = 5.5\%$, indicating a doubling time of about 13 years. A further study analysed the growth of organic substances by computationally treating the Beilstein database for the period 1850-2004 and an exponential growth was also found, with $r = 8.3\%$ before 1900 and $r = 4.4\%$ afterwards (Fialkowski et al., 2005).

In a more recent account, we analysed 16,356,012 reactions and 14,341,955 substances published between 1800 and 2015 in chemical journals, gathered in the Reaxys electronic database. We found that the chemical space has historically grown at an exponential rate, with a stable growth rate ($r = 4.4\%$) (Llanos et al., 2019). This indicates that about every 16 years chemists have doubled the number of new substances reported. This amounts to saying that if the doubling time is kept, in the following 16 years the chemical community will double the number of all reported chemicals in the history of chemistry. This is the dramatic speed at which the chemical space grows.

The above results were obtained by retrieving from Reaxys all reactions and by labelling them with their first publication year. From those reactions we retrieved the substances involved, which were likewise labelled using their first publication year. Thus, we counted, year by year, the number of new substances, leading to the annual output of new substances shown in Figure 1a. Based on this time series signal, we calculated the best fit curve, which turned out to be an exponential function with the just described growth rate.

Figure 1. The expanding chemical space. (a) Black curve: annual growth of number of new substances between 1800–2015. Here, the actual number of reported substances in the chemical literature of year t is encoded in $s(t)$. The exponential equation fitting the growth is indicated as a red straight line (red curve) with equation: $s_t = 51.85e^{0.04324(t-1800)}$. Vertical lines indicate the transitions of statistical regime (see (b)). (b) Variability of the annual output of new substances, calculated as $\ln s(t)+1 - \ln s(t)$. Figures close to the curve correspond to the average variabilities for the periods (regimes) 1800–1860, 1861–1980 and 1981–2015, demarcated by vertical lines. The three statistical regimes are indicated in (a): proto-organic, organic and organometallic regimes. The effects of the World Wars (WWs) are indicated close to the black curve. Plots adapted from Fig. 1A and S1 in (Llanos et al., 2019), and from Fig. 3 in (Restrepo, 2022b).

The three statistical regimes in the expansion of the chemical space

Besides the growth of the chemical space, the data on the annual output of chemicals also provides rich information on the temporal variability on the report of new chemicals. Therefore, we analysed the variability of the temporal signal depicted in Figure 1a and we found three statistical regimes, where the difference of the annual output of chemicals is normally distributed (Figure 1b). This indicates three different periods of production of chemicals in the history of chemistry. The first regime spans the years 1800-1860, the second runs between 1860 and 1980 and the third and present one began in 1980 (Figure 1). The first regime was characterised by the volatile production of new chemicals, with large differences in the new reported substances from year to year (Figure 1b). This suddenly changed around 1860, when a drastic reduction of the variability of the number of reported substances occurred and such a variability was kept for about a century (Figure 1b). By 1980 the variability was further reduced, giving place to the third and current regime of production of chemicals, which holds the lowest difference in the annual output of chemicals ever (Figure 1b).

The drastic changes in the variability of the annual output of chemicals indicate that the mechanism triggering the change of regime was rapidly adopted and assimilated by the chemical community. Which were those changes revolutionising the discovery of new chemicals? Moreover, as the variability of the outcome of chemicals remained normally distributed over large periods, for instance 120 years for the second regime, the regimes indicate a kind of conservatism or self-reinforcing processes spanning large periods of chemical practice (Jost & Restrepo, 2023). To have more details about the three regimes and their transitions, we analysed the kind of compounds reported in each period (Leal et al., 2022; Llanos et al., 2019) and withdrew from accounts on the history of chemistry (Klein, 2003; Rocke, 2002, 2013).

The first regime (1800-1860) was characterised by an emphasis on inorganic chemistry. Its variability in the annual output of chemicals indicates an exploratory period of the chemical space, where some years brought several new substances and some others not so many. This goes hand in hand with the relatively small community supporting the expansion of the chemical space (Nielsen & Strbanova, 2008; Schummer, 1997). According to several history of chemistry accounts (Klein, 2003; Rocke, 2002, 2013), the drastic reduction of the variability around 1860 was caused by the widespread introduction of the structural theory that regularised chemical production, assisted by an ever-growing chemical community, which was benefiting from the positive public image of chemistry and of its important chemical industry (Jost & Restrepo, 2023). The interplay between a powerful chemical theory and the social conditions led to regularise the annual output of chemicals, which were mostly organic substances. This trend lasted more than a century (Figure 1a). A second sudden reduction of the variability of the annual production of chemicals was observed around 1980, but it is still an open question as to the leading event or collection of events causing this further regularisation of the variability. It could have been caused by the increasing computerisation of the chemical practice or a delayed effect of the widespread adoption of spectroscopic chemical instrumentation that took place in the 1950s (Reinhardt, 2001). At any rate, the third regime was characterised by a revival of compounds containing metals, specifically organometallics, followed by a surge of substances of biological interest (Llanos et al., 2019).

In more technical terms, the three statistical regimes were observed by taking as data source the time series depicted in Figure 1a (black curve). There, for each year t a corresponding number of new substances $s(t)$ is reported. Note the difference between s_t and $s(t)$. The former corresponds to the fitting curve for the actual data gathered in $s(t)$. Aiming at determining the annual variation in the number of new substances, we calculated $\ln s(t+1) - \ln s(t)$, which is plotted in Figure 1b. By an iterative process, we looked for temporal periods with stationary behaviour. This we computed by testing the normality of the $\ln s(t+1) - \ln s(t)$ values for different sequences of t values. The normality tests applied were the Shapiro–Wilk and Kolmogorov–Smirnov ones. These results indicated the above discussed three statistical regimes. All other sequences of years failed the normality tests.

World war effects

We found that the expansion of the chemical space has been affected by social setbacks such as World Wars (WWs) (Llanos et al., 2019). We observed two drops in chemical production around WWs times and quantified the effect of these events in the annual output of new chemicals. It was found that WWI sent back chemical production 37 years, while WWII 16 years. The dramatic effect of WWI follows from the centralised structure of chemistry in the first quarter of the twentieth century, whose capital was Germany. WWI actually motivated a restructuring of chemical industrial and research production, prompting a decentralisation in which the USA began to take the lead. By the time of WWII, the social system of chemistry had changed and production was sufficiently less centralised such that, to a large extent, WW II did not affect the annual output of new chemicals. Interestingly, neither the growth rate of the number of new chemicals nor the variability of this material output was affected by WWs (Figure 1). This contrasts with delays in bibliographic production, for instance as observed in other disciplines (Price, 1963). In the chemical space, WWs caused a drop in production followed by a rapid recovery after the setbacks, leading chemical production to pre-WWs trends (Llanos et al., 2019).

The seams of the chemical space

So far we have discussed one constituent of the chemical space, namely its substances. In this section we discuss some results on the seams of the space, that is the reactions connecting substances.

The more basic account of reactions is gauged by analysing the participation of substances in them. We explore this participation taking into account the two main roles of substances in reactions, namely as substrates and as products. By analysing the participation of substances in reactions reported between 1800 and 2015, we found that chemists have had preferences in the selection of their starting materials (Llanos et al., 2019). This is evident in the fact that only a few substances have triggered many reactions, while the vast majority have been used only once. Figure 2a shows the distribution of participation of substances in chemical reactions for different periods. Examples of frequently used educts, which we call toolkit compounds, are: acetic anhydride, methyl iodide and formaldehyde (Llanos et al., 2019). For instance, acetic anhydride has been the most used educt ever since 1940 and it has been part of the top-10 of most used educts since 1880 (about 30 years after its synthesis (Partington, 1964).

As for substrates, the distributions of production of new substances in chemical reactions are heavily tailed, indicating that chemists have often synthesised some few products, while the majority of products are synthesised only once. The most synthesised targets over different periods in the history of chemistry include organic acids such as oxalic and benzoic ones, and, interestingly, hydrogen sulfide and uranium hexafluoride are examples of targets motivated by nuclear research in the post-WW2 period (Llanos et al., 2019; O'Donnell et al., 1966; Rozen, 1995). Likewise, organotin compounds and ferrocene evidenced the interest in organometallics, especially in materials science and homogeneous catalysis (Togni & Halterman, 2008). We also draw attention to the presence of metallic oxides in the last period; they are often used in the synthesis of catalysts and nanomaterials (Richardson, 2000).

Figure 2. Use and production of compounds. Frequency distributions of participation of compounds in R different reactions as (a) substrates and (b) products. The left-hand side of the distributions corresponds to the many compounds appearing in few reactions, whereas the right-hand side corresponds to the few compounds appearing in many reactions.

In the analysis of the organic chemistry part of the chemical space a similar distribution was obtained and it was claimed that the distribution is of power-law type (Fialkowski et al., 2005). Our analysis rejects the power-law hypothesis, which indicates that the mechanism underlying the selection of substrates cannot be modelled by multiplicative or Yule processes only or any other mechanisms generating power laws. Other distributions that we tested but likewise rejected on statistical grounds were normal, exponential and Poisson ones (Llanos et al., 2019). Therefore, the use of substrates results from a more complex process, whose study is of central importance for the evolution of the chemical space.

Interplay of the evolving chemical space and the unfolding of the periodic system

One of the icons of chemistry is the periodic system, formulated in the 1860s thanks to the chemical knowledge gathered at that time (Restrepo, 2019). Taking into account that the chemical space is a central part of chemical knowledge (Jost & Restrepo, 2022), we wondered how the expansion of the chemical space has affected the periodic system.

The periodic system was formulated by analysing order and similarities among chemical elements (Leal & Restrepo, 2019) as provided by the chemical space of the 1860s (Boeck & Rocke, 2022a, 2022b; Jensen & Mendeleev, 2005; Leal et al., 2022). Order was provided by atomic weights, which were determined by finding the smallest common combining weight of a large set of compounds containing a reference element. Similarity was mainly determined on the basis of common empirical and molecular formulas (Leal et al., 2022).

As atomic weights and chemical formulas are reciprocally related, and current formulas arose from deep 19th-century discussions about atomic weights, any attempt to explore the evolution of the periodic system must necessarily consider those atomic debates. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the various nineteenth century competing sets of atomic weights, which led to chaos of formulae before the 1860s. Thus, different sets of atomic weights may have produced different orderings of the elements and different formulae, leading to different similarities. Hence, different weights may have led to different periodic systems, even for the same set of substances constituting the chemical space.

To tackle this issue, we analysed 13 19th century sets of atomic weights and developed an algorithm to construct their corresponding chemical space. The algorithm takes the formulas of the chemical space we know today were available in the 19th century and approximates them according to the different sets of atomic weights (Leal et al., 2022). Thus, for each set of weights a chemical space was created and by analysing the ordering and similarity relationships among elements a corresponding periodic system was obtained. After 1860, chemists converged to a unique set of atomic weights, which was later in the dawn of the 20th century replaced by the atomic number as the ordering principle for the chemical elements. Thus, we conducted two studies on the evolution of the periodic system according to the expansion of the chemical space. One before 1869 and another one from 1870 up to 2021.

We found that order relationships among chemical elements have been rather stable over the history (Leal et al., 2022). Even in the times of competing sets of weights and of rapid discovery of new elements, the chemical space led to orderings of elements that are pretty similar to those of modern times. Similarity, nevertheless, has not been that stable. We found that the different sets of atomic weights in the 19th century led to different similarity relationships. Nonetheless, by 1843, the atomic weights reported by Gmelin led to detect similarities among the chemical elements that were later unveiled by the periodic systems of Meyer and Mendeleev (Leal et al., 2022). Results after 1869 confirmed the stability of order relationships among elements and the

sensitivity of their similarities as a consequence of the expansion of the chemical space (Bran et al., 2022). Although similarities are affected by the discovery of new elements and of new combinations of them, we found that the periodic system has converged towards its current stable structure through six stages (Bran et al., 2022), respectively characterised by the finding of elements (1800-1826), the emergence of the core structure of the system (1826-1860), its organic chemistry bias (1860-1900) and its further stabilisation (1900-1948), World War 2 new chemistry (1948-1980) and the system final stabilisation (1980-). Representative periodic systems of each period are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Snapshots in the evolution of the periodic system. Periodic tables representative of each period in history. Families of similar elements are represented as coloured sets.

Conclusions and outlook

Chemical space has grown over more than 200 years of history of chemistry at an exponential pace, with a rather stable growth rate not even affected by World Wars or by the introduction of new theories and new technologies. This triggers interesting questions about the dynamical rules driving the expansion of the chemical space. Very likely, shading like on those rules requires the introduction of further dimensions, here not treated, on the dynamics of chemistry. They may include the growth of the social system supporting chemical production, which involves institutions such as universities, laboratories and industries, as well as chemistry practitioners of all times. A further dimension we believe needs to be included spans the semiotic aspects of chemistry, which include the communication channels used by chemists as well as the signs they use to communicate their results and to educate newcomers. We believe these two dimensions plus the material one, to which the chemical space belongs, constitute a complex dynamical system susceptible of being modelled. Meeting this challenge requires more data on the social and semiotic dimensions, which, in this computational age, are becoming more and more digitised every day and prepared for computational studies.

Besides studying the growth of the chemical space, we also analysed the variability of the annual output of chemicals. This led us to detect three historical regimes in the discovery of new substances. The first one occurred before 1860 and was ruled by inorganic chemistry. This was a period of high variability in the annual discovery of substances, which seems to indicate the most exploratory period of chemistry. The second regime began in 1860 motivated by the introduction of molecular structural theory, which became the rationale to understand the already known chemicals and to foresee future directions of the chemical space. That is, it became a paper tool, as Klein has extensively discussed it (Klein, 2003). In this regime organic chemistry blossomed and mastering its methods and the production of its substances led to self-reinforcing processes in chemistry, which contributed to reducing the variability of the annual output of chemicals. The third regime began about 1980 and it is still a matter of inquiry determining the reasons triggering the transition from the organic regime to this third one, which evidenced a revival of organometallic substances and later on of large production of bioorganic compounds. The further reduction of the variability of the annual production of chemicals suggests further self-reinforcing mechanisms that are worth studying in the historiography of chemistry.

The interaction of chemical space with the evolution of chemistry showed that such a fundamental chemical concept as the periodic system is not set in stone. We found that in terms of ordering of elements, the system has been rather stable, which means that the discovery of new elements and of new compounds has preserved, to a large extent, the order relationships among the elements known since the early times of the history of chemistry. Such a stability is, nevertheless, not observed for the similarity among chemical elements, which has been very sensitive to the discovery of new compounds and of combinations of elements. As the expansion of the chemical space obeys also social constraints, for instance warfare research in belligerent times, we found that the periodic system is therefore susceptible to social changes. In particular, we found that WWI research triggered the discovery of new fluorine compounds, which led to changes in the periodic system, for instance by increasing the dissimilarity of fluorine as a member of the halogens. We also found evidence of the itinerate belonging of hydrogen to either the alkali metals or the halogens depending on the inorganic/organic ratio of the chemical space. Hydrogen was more akin to metals in the early stages of the chemical space ruled by inorganic chemistry and turned similar to the halogens with the rise of organic chemistry.

The work reported here constitutes a completely data-driven, computational approach to the history of chemistry. Using chemical compounds and reactions as the only source of data goes to the very heart of chemistry as a science. This is in contrast to text-based approaches to the history of science that focus on themes and topics of scientific discourse.

Acknowledgments

We thank Peter F. Stadler, Duc H. Luu, Andrés Bernal, Wilmer Leal, Eugenio J. Llanos and Andrés M. Bran for insightful discussions and computations leading to the publications supporting this document.

References

- Boeck, G., & Rocke, A. J. (2022a). Lothar Meyer, Modern Theories of Chemistry and their Significance for Chemical Statics, First Edition (1864), Complete. In G. Boeck & A. J. Rocke (Eds.), *Lothar Meyer: Modern Theories and Pathways to Periodicity* (pp. 45–139). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78342-6_2

- Boeck, G., & Roche, A. J. (2022b). Lothar Meyer, Moderne Theorien der Chemie, vollständiger Text der ersten Auflage (1864). In G. Boeck & A. J. Roche (Eds.), *Lothar Meyer: Moderne Theorien und Wege zum Periodensystem* (pp. 49–155). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-63933-7_2
- Bran, A. M., Stadler, P. F., Jost, J., & Restrepo, G. (2022). *Periodic system converges and is affected by wars*. <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2022-clbrk>
- Fialkowski, M., Bishop, K. J. M., Chubukov, V. A., Campbell, C. J., & Grzybowski, B. A. (2005). Architecture and Evolution of Organic Chemistry. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 44(44), 7263–7269. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.200502272>
- Gibson, A., Laubichler, M. D., & Maienschein, J. (2019). Introduction. *Isis*, 110(3), 497–501. <https://doi.org/10.1086/705542>
- Jensen, W. B., & Mendeleev, D. I. (2005). *Mendeleev on the Periodic Law: Selected Writings, 1869 - 1905*. Dover Publications Inc.
- Jost, J., & Restrepo, G. (2022). *The Evolution of Chemical Knowledge*. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-10094-9>
- Jost, J., & Restrepo, G. (2023). *Self reinforcing mechanisms driving the evolution of the chemical space*. *In press*.
- Klein, U. (2003). *Experiments, Models, Paper Tools: Cultures of Organic Chemistry in the Nineteenth Century*. Stanford University Press.
- Laubichler, M. D., Maienschein, J., & Renn, J. (2013). Computational Perspectives in the History of Science: To the Memory of Peter Damerow. *Isis*, 104(1), 119–130. <https://doi.org/10.1086/669891>
- Leal, W., Llanos, E. J., Bernal, A., Stadler, P. F., Jost, J., & Restrepo, G. (2022). The expansion of chemical space in 1826 and in the 1840s prompted the convergence to the periodic system. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(30), e2119083119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2119083119>
- Leal, W., & Restrepo, G. (2019). Formal structure of periodic system of elements. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 475(2224), 20180581. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2018.0581>
- Llanos, E. J., Leal, W., Luu, D. H., Jost, J., Stadler, P. F., & Restrepo, G. (2019). Exploration of the chemical space and its three historical regimes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(26), 12660–12665. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1816039116>
- Nielsen, A. K., & Strbanova, S. (2008). *Creating Networks in Chemistry*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/9781847558244>
- O'Donnell, T. A., Stewart, D. F., & Wilson, P. (1966). Reactivity of Transition Metal Fluorides. II. Uranium Hexafluoride. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 5(8), 1438–1441. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ic50042a035>
- Partington, J. R. (1964). *A History of chemistry*. Macmillan.
- Price, D. J. de S. (1963). *Little Science, Big Science*. Columbia University Press.
- Reinhardt, C. (2001). *Chemical Sciences in the 20th Century: Bridging Boundaries* | Wiley.
- Restrepo, G. (2019). Compounds Bring Back Chemistry to the System of Chemical Elements. *Substantia*, 115–124. <https://doi.org/10.13128/Substantia-739>
- Restrepo, G. (2022a). Computational History of Chemistry. *Bulletin for the History of Chemistry / Division of the History of Chemistry of the American Chemical Society*, 47, 91–106.
- Restrepo, G. (2022b). Chemical space: Limits, evolution and modelling of an object bigger than our universal library. *Digital Discovery*, 1(5), 568–585. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2DD00030J>
- Richardson, H. W. (2000). Copper Compounds. In *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. https://doi.org/10.1002/14356007.a07_567
- Roche, A. (2002). The Theory of Chemical Structure and its Applications. In M. J. Nye (Ed.), *The Cambridge History of Science: Volume 5: The Modern Physical and Mathematical Sciences* (Vol. 5, pp. 255–271). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521571999.015>
- Roche, A. (2013). What did “theory” mean to nineteenth-century chemists? *Foundations of Chemistry*, 15(2), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10698-013-9184-2>
- Rozen, A. M. (1995). The first plant in the world for the production of heavy water by the method of two-temperature water-hydrogen sulfide isotopic exchange. *Atomic Energy*, 78(3), 218–223. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02407494>

Schummer, J. (1997). Scientometric studies on chemistry I: The exponential growth of chemical substances, 1800–1995. *Scientometrics*, 39(1), 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02457433>

Togni, A., & Halterman, R. L. (2008). *Metallocenes: Synthesis Reactivity Applications*. Wiley.